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Good practice recommendations on evaluation of PhD courses in transferable skills

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Deliverable D4.5

Good practice recommendations on evaluation of PhD courses in transferable skills

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SUMMARY

This document is organised around three main sections. First, it describes the target groups and background of the good practice recommendations. The next section describes general and specific criteria that should be taken into consideration for the evaluation of PhD courses in transferable skills (e.g., course contents, practical organisation of the courses, exposure to the non-academic sector). Then, the document lists some recommendations for the accreditation of PhD courses on transferable skills, including the use of ECTS credits, micro credentials and certificates.

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INTRODUCTION

This document outlines a series of good practices recommendations on the evaluation and the accreditation of PhD courses in transferable skills.

Why is there a need for best practice recommendations specific to PhD courses on transferable skills?

Numerous documents have highlighted the importance of transferable skills for improving research and innovation (OECD, 2011; OECD, 2012). While research institutes and universities offer transferable skills training to their doctoral candidates, the available courses often focus on academic and research-oriented skills (Hasgall et al., 2019; Boman et al., 2021). Given that an increasing number of PhD holders will be employed outside of academia, course design, implementation and evaluation should take into consideration the various career trajectories available to doctoral candidates and the different skillsets needed in academic and non-academic jobs.

Who are these best practice recommendations for?

The recommendations outlined below are not only useful to evaluate and improve existing courses but should also be considered as guiding principles for the development of new PhD courses on transferable skills. In particular, these recommendations are aimed at:

- Course evaluators
- Course developers
- Course instructors

What are the best practice recommendations based on?

The best practice recommendations in this document are based on the results of DocEnhance, a Horizon 2020 funded project aimed at improving career development and employment opportunities of PhD candidates. The project outputs include a career-tracking survey gathering information on graduate career paths, a recommended transferrable skills curriculum for PhD candidates, and three courses on transferable skills available on the [DocEnhance LMS platform](#).

The three courses are:

- *PhD Supervision*, focusing on how supervisors can best mentor and support doctoral candidates;
- *Data Stewardship*, providing good practices and training on how to manage research data;
- *Career Management & Entrepreneurship*, helping doctoral candidates planning their career after their PhD and improving their entrepreneurial skills.

Each course was piloted in two different universities²: a first piloting round was completed in the first semester of 2021 while a second piloting round was done in spring 2022. After both piloting rounds, PhD candidates/supervisors and course developers were invited to complete an evaluation survey. The best practice recommendations are based on the outcomes of these evaluations and on the feedback of the course developers.

GOOD PRACTICE RECOMMENDATIONS ON THE EVALUATION OF PHD COURSES IN TRANSFERABLE SKILLS

This section provides a series of criteria that should be taken into consideration when evaluating PhD courses on transferable skills. The general criteria are based on the structure of the evaluation forms of the DocEnhance pilot courses - which included a series of open and close ended questions aimed at course participants, instructors and organisers. In addition to general guidelines, this section also outlines a few additional criteria that may be especially relevant for PhD courses on transferable skills. The additional criteria were formulated on the basis of the feedback of course developers and on the answers of the open questions in the collected evaluation forms.

General criteria

- *Practical organisation of the pilot phase*. These questions should cover the implementation of the course and might include a wide range of topics, such as interest in the course among the target audience, organisational challenges, recruitment of course instructors and students, and adaptation of course materials for specific needs.

² Three universities in the case of the course on PhD Supervision

- *Contents of the course.* These questions should evaluate which contents of the course are more or least relevant to the stakeholders and should include requests for suggestions on how to improve them.
- *Learning materials and methodology.* These questions should focus on whether the materials and methodology used during the course align with the expectation of course participants in terms of contents and learning outcomes.
- *Learning outcomes and satisfaction.* These questions should evaluate the usefulness of the learning outcomes and whether they are aligned with the expectations of stakeholders.

Additional criteria

Providing the right course at the right time

The evaluation should take into consideration whether the course offering maximises the possibility for PhD candidates to profit from the training offered. This means that the course content should be designed and evaluated taking into consideration the profile of course participants, so that they can be planned and offered at the adequate time during the doctoral training (i.e., first-year vs last-year PhD candidates). For instance, the outcomes of the DocEnhance pilot courses showed that participants considered the course on Data Management more useful for candidates at the beginning of their PhD, when they need more guidance and training on how to manage data, rather than at later stages.

In some cases, courses may be divided according to the profile and seniority of the target participants to better tailor the contents to the audience or may offer hybrid solutions where all participants follow the same course but where one or more separate sessions are foreseen, depending on the group composition. In the DocEnhance project, this approach was chosen by one of the universities piloting the course on PhD supervision, where junior and senior supervisors were split in two different groups.

Below are some examples of closed- and open-end questions that can be used in the evaluation forms to determine the usefulness of the course with respect to the profile of PhD candidates:

- Are the contents of the course relevant for PhD candidates at all stages of their PhD?
- For whom are the contents of the course most relevant?

- At what stage of a PhD programme should this course be offered?
- There is a precedent doctoral training course required that should be previously done?

Exposure to the non-academic sector

Whether training activities foresee some exposure to the non-academic sector is another relevant aspect to be taken into consideration when planning and/or evaluating PhD courses on transferable skills. This recommendation is of large interest considering that many PhD graduates will be employed in the non-academic sector.

Exposure to the non-academic sector can take various forms, from organising on-site visits to industries to inviting guest speakers from the non-academic sector for lectures or face-to-face workshops. These activities not only promote employment opportunities for PhD candidates outside of academia but are also an efficient tool to show how the skills taught during the course can be translated into practice.

Examples of closed- and open-end questions:

- Rate the usefulness of the activities involving the non-academic sector in terms of contents and learning outcomes
- Was the choice of guests from the non-academic sector appropriate with respect to the contents and topic of the course?
- Do you have any suggestions concerning course activities involving guests from the non-academic sector?
- What are the implications of ethical and social impact of PhD research activities considering future workplaces?

Interaction and group discussions

The results of the evaluation of the three DocEnhance courses have highlighted the importance of interactions during the sessions. In particular, course participants stressed the need for time slots dedicated to questions or peer groups to further discuss the topics addressed in the sessions. Evaluating the opportunities of interaction is especially important in the case of courses delivered online or in a hybrid format, which may provide more barriers to participation with respect to in-person training activities. In particular for this kind of training several questions may be addressed:

- Did the course offer enough opportunities for discussion and interaction between participants?
- Is timing and balance of hybrid/onsite sessions well planned?
- Do you have any suggestions on how to make the course more interactive to engage participants?

GOOD PRACTICE RECOMMENDATIONS ON THE ACCREDITATION OF PHD COURSES IN TRANSFERABLE SKILLS

A form of recognition for the participation in the courses is necessary to promote participation and to provide PhD candidates with a formal recognition of the acquired skills. Participation in the courses can be acknowledged in various ways.

A first possibility is to award ECTS credits upon course completion. While ECTS credits are a common system for the recognition of learning outcomes within universities, two main factors impact on the effectiveness of ECTS credits as a tool for the accreditation of PhD courses in transferable skills. One aspect to consider is that not all doctoral programmes foresee the use of ECTS credits to award participation in courses (European Commission, 2017). Furthermore, some training activities may be open not only to PhD candidates but also to other junior researchers, such as in the case of the DocEnhance course on PhD supervision. In these cases, course certificates can provide a valid alternative for the recognition of training activities.

Another possibility is to use microcredentials, which can be especially useful for acknowledging qualifications obtained through small volumes of learning (European Commission, 2021), as in the case of courses on transferable skills. One advantage of microcredentials over certificates is the possibility to combine them into larger units. For instance, a course on career development may consist of smaller course units addressing different topics, such as writing a CV or a cover letter, improving networking skills or preparing for a job interview. Upon completion of each module – which can be taken on a stand-alone basis – participants receive a microcredential. Participants completing all modules can combine the microcredentials into a larger one (e.g., career

development). A summary of the available tools for the accreditation of PhD courses is provided below:

	Certificate	ECTS credits	Digital credentials
Can be used for a wide range of participants (PhD candidates, Postdocs, etc.)	yes	no	yes
Can be combined in larger units	no	yes	yes

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